

ReBioCycle Pulse

Feature 1/2024 - Recycling biodegradable bioplastics

December 19, 2024

What is ReBioCycle?

ReBioCycle stands for "A new European Blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions". It is an Innovation Action project focusing on biobased biodegradable polymers and plastics. ReBioCycle goals are to demonstrate that:

✓ [#biobased](#) [#biodegradable](#) [#plastics](#) can be kept in the cycle for as long as possible through innovative [#recycling](#) technologies

✓ [#endoflife](#) [#biobased](#) [#biodegradable](#) [#plastics](#) can be used in the [#circular](#) [#bioeconomy](#)

The project is funded by the [Circular Bio-based Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. ReBioCycle started on 1 October 2024 and will run for 4 years.

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Challenges of recycling biodegradable bioplastics addressed by ReBioCycle

Integrating biobased biodegradable plastics into the circular economy requires establishing collection and sorting strategies for biobased biodegradable plastics that are compatible with current waste management practices and their subsequent recycling through novel technologies. The recycling of biobased plastics into recycled high-performing materials is a key challenge. Biobased plastic waste does not yet constitute a relevant amount of the total plastic waste (only 1% in weight). Still, due to their high weight in the political agenda, it is easy to foresee that biobased plastics will gain a relevant market share in the near future.

ReBioCycle provides a portfolio of bioplastic sorting and recycling technologies within three complementary [waste-processor-centric hubs](#) at a demonstration scale and in the actual operational environment the effective and efficient recycling of three types of bioplastics (PLA, PHA, composites) to demonstrate the higher impact of obtaining the same or superior grade recycled polymers and other higher-value applications.

Read more about the project and its approach: <https://rebiocycle.eu/about/>

Kick-off meeting, 2-3 October 2024 in Dublin

The [ReBioCycle](#) project kick-off took place at the University College Dublin on 2-3 October 2024, hosted by the coordinator, Prof. Kevin O'Connor, [University College Dublin](#), [BiOrbic University College Dublin](#) and [BiOrbic Bioeconomy SFI Research Centre](#).

Kick-off meeting, 2-3 October 2024

We are proud to have an outstanding team under the coordination of [University College Dublin](#) formed by [Sulapac Ltd](#) [Novamont](#) [University of Galway](#) [TotalEnergies Corbion](#) [AIMPLAS](#) · [Technological Institute of Plastics](#) [TORWASH](#) [ARCHA](#) | [Analisi Ambientali](#) | [Ricerca & Sviluppo](#) | [Tecnologie Azienda](#) [Multiservizi](#) [Igiene Ambientale](#) [Torino](#) [Paques Biomaterials](#) [CSIC Magfi](#) <Sustainability in Action> [GlasPort Bio](#) [Arapaha](#) [Iren Emilia S.p.A.](#) [European Bioplastics](#) [I.Blu Spa](#) [Corbion B.V.](#) [SOCIEDAD ANONIMA AGRICULTORES DE LA VEGA DE VALENCIA](#) [NTCP](#) [Kaneka Belgium NV](#)

Together, we work for:

- ✓ Improved circularity and resource efficiency via practical application of the circular #bioeconomy concept in the #biobased and #biodegradable plastics value chain.
- ✓ Effective #sorting and #recycling schemes for biobased and biodegradable plastic materials.
- ✓ Increase of recycled content in new products from biobased and biodegradable plastics.
- ✓ Improved environmental performance across the value chain against fossil or biobased benchmarks.
- ✓ Better social acceptance of #circular biobased solutions and products.

“ReBioCycle will scale up and demonstrate biobased biodegradable plastics recycling technologies: Biobased biodegradable plastics can be kept in the material cycle for as long as possible through innovative recycling technologies, thus demonstrating that end-of-life

biobased biodegradable plastics can be used in the circular bioeconomy.” Prof. Kevin O’Connor, ReBioCycle Coordinator, University College Dublin, BiOrbic

You can find the press release for the launch of the project here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13899137>

The presentations of the kick-off meeting are available in open access on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rebiocycle/>

EBC24 Side event on recycling strategies for bioplastics: what’s next? On 9 December 2024, in-person in Berlin and online

This event was hosted in Berlin by [European Bioplastics](#) alongside the #EBC24 to showcase the plans of [ReBioCycle](#), [MoeBIOS](#) and [PROSPER](#), which have kicked off in 2024 to bring upscaling recycling technologies for bioplastics even further. This event aimed to connect experts working on novel or improved recycling technologies for bioplastics from academia and the private sector, offering expertise along the whole process of bioplastics waste management from the foundation (e.g., waste sorting and pretreatment, creation of value chains) to recycling technologies. In the past years, several projects have already been funded by the Horizon Programme for Research and Innovation and the [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) to improve and upscale bioplastics’ recycling technologies, especially for biobased applications related to packaging. This is the case for [BioSupPack](#) and [BIOMAC](#).

The presentations at the event revolved around the following recycling technologies: mechanical, chemical, enzymatic and microbial recycling. Following the presentations, the audience was able to put forward questions to the speakers in a matchmaking session with [Jan Pels](#) (TORWASH), [Miriam Lorenzo Navarro](#) (ITENE), and [Wouter Post](#) (Wageningen University & Research) regarding the need to improve recycling technologies for bioplastics that are already biodegradable. A clear conclusion of the event was the acknowledgement of many reuse scenarios for bioplastics and the need for bioplastic products to be designed with realistic reuse possibilities in mind and with an efficient and appropriate end-of-life solution scientifically proven to minimise its environmental impact. All experts agreed that the main challenge for bioplastics not being recycled lies not within its biobased and biodegradable characteristics but with the need for more scale to set up a compelling business case for sorting and subsequent recycling.

“The current recycling technologies available for recycling biodegradable plastics are limited, but with this project, we are going to make them widely available. Then nobody can claim that the switch to biodegradable plastics cannot be made because they cannot be recycled”. Jan Pels, CTO and Managing Director of TORWASH, leader of the ReBioCycle Dutch hub,

Several resources are now available in open access if you missed the event:

- ✓ Introductory document: <https://zenodo.org/records/14231054>
- ✓ Presentations of the event: <https://zenodo.org/records/14384110>
- ✓ Recording of the event (approx. 1 hour): <https://youtu.be/DtbKQxHc3ag>

EBC24 europeanbioplastics
European Bioplastics Conference
Side Event / Workshop
Recycling strategies
for bioplastics: what's next?
Novel approaches in recycling and upcycling bioplastics
9 December, 5 - 8 pm CET including networking reception

Logos: BIOSUPPACK, ReBioCycle, mOBIOUS, BIOMAC, PROSPER, Bio-based Industries Consortium, CBE JU, Circular Bio-based Europe, Co-funded by the European Union, Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation

EBC24 Side event on recycling strategies for bioplastics

Contribution to the White Paper on "Alternative feedstock for biobased plastics: Bridging the gap between research and the market"

[European Bioplastics](#) organised an in-person workshop on 16 October 2024 in Brussels as a closing event to the successful EUBP Talk Series on Alternative Feedstock for Bioplastics.

Representatives of outstanding research and innovation projects presented their latest insights on how biowaste can be successfully used for bioplastics production. In recent years, several projects funded by the [Horizon Programme for Research and Innovation](#) and the [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) have been exploring ways to give residual and biowaste a second chance. ReBioCycle contributed to the white paper

emerging from this workshop in the section related to the challenges of bioplastics recycling, together with [MoeBIOS](#).

The paper is available in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/14245778s>

White paper contributed by ReBioCycle

Get to know more about ReBioCycle

Visit us: www.rebiocycle.eu

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rebiocycle/>

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Disclaimer

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